

Redefining Telecommunications: Data Engineering and Blockchain for B5G/6G Networks

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Abstract—This tutorial provides a detailed and structured examination of the latest developments in data engineering and blockchain technologies, focusing on their convergence with emerging telecommunication systems. A major focus is on mapping the data engineering lifecycle — including phases such as data connectivity, ingestion, processing and analysis, storage, visualization and orchestration — to the architecture and operational requirements of telecommunication networks. The role of blockchain and distributed ledger technologies (DLTs) in enabling secure, transparent and decentralized solutions for B5G systems is also highlighted. In addition, the tutorial explores the integration of these frameworks with data science pipelines and discusses practical use cases where data engineering and blockchain intersect in telecom environments. To complement the conceptual parts, two illustrative demonstrations are also presented.

Index Terms—data engineering, blockchain, Beyond 5G (B5G), demonstrations.

I. INTRODUCTION

State-of-the-art algorithms, especially those based on neural networks and deep learning, are at the heart of modern AI/ML platforms and play a critical role in extracting insights from large numerical data sources such as images, videos and complex data sets. These capabilities enable companies to make informed decisions in the areas of product development, service innovation and application design — while paving the way for new business models. The ongoing development of the AI/ML ecosystem is driven by a vibrant open source community [1], cross-sector collaborations between industry, academia and public institutions [2] and significant advances from leading technology labs such as Facebook AI Research (FAIR)¹, Google AI² and

Microsoft AI³. Taken together, these efforts improve the ability to derive both real-time insights from streaming data and long-term analytics from historical data. This gives organizations the information they need to monitor their infrastructure and maintain a competitive advantage.

The forthcoming generations of mobile networks— - Beyond 5G (B5G), which is currently being rolled out, and 6G, which is still largely at the research and concept stage — are expected to offer unprecedented opportunities. These future networks will offer ultra-fast data rates, support huge volumes of traffic, enable hyper-connectivity, achieve extremely low latency and support a wide range of different applications. Emerging use cases in these software-enabled network environments include immersive technologies such as Virtual, Augmented, and Mixed Reality (VR/AR/MR), machine-to-machine (M2M) communication, real-time 3D holography and even sensory-rich 5D communication experiences that include sight, sound, touch, smell and taste. Further innovations are expected in smart textiles and wearables, fully autonomous Level 5 vehicles and Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) to support large-scale M2M ecosystems. The realization of these services requires robust security mechanisms, scalable architectures, intelligent resource allocation, energy-efficient design and cost-effective operation.

Even though current security frameworks are sufficient to maintain basic protection, they have some critical limitations. These include poor scalability, inefficient resource utilisation— leading to higher latency and network congestion, and increased operational costs due to rigid and manually burdensome security procedures. In addition, the lack of automation poses a challenge to the rapid deployment of

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¹Facebook AI Research, <https://research.fb.com/publications/>

²Google AI Research, <https://research.google/pubs/>

³Microsoft AI Research, <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/>

services in fast-paced environments. As a result, traditional centralized security models in legacy cellular systems are increasingly inadequate to meet the dynamic performance requirements of B5G and emerging 6G networks, which could hinder their full potential. To address these challenges, decentralized solutions such as blockchain and DLTs offer promising alternatives. By utilizing built-in cryptographic protection mechanisms, consensus protocols and distributed trust models, these technologies offer a more flexible, scalable and autonomous approach to securing next-generation mobile infrastructures.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE DATA ENGINEERING ECOSYSTEM

Figure 1 presents a high-level depiction of the core components that make up a typical data engineering platform. The architecture is broadly organized into six key functional modules: Data Connectivity, Data Ingestion, Analytical Processing, Data Storage, Monitoring & Visualization, and Management & Orchestration.

Figure 1: A representation of the core components of a typical data engineering platform.

1) *Data Connection Frameworks*: The data connection phase initiates access to the data source, which can be located in various places — from local files and web repositories to mobile or IoT devices, metastore tables or centralized data stores. These sources can take various forms, e.g. static files, relational and NoSQL databases (e.g. MySQL, MongoDB), system or network logs, clickstream data from websites or real-time streams accessed via third-party APIs and data frameworks. Once this connection is established, it can be configured so

that the data is seamlessly forwarded to the subsequent Data Ingestion module for further processing.

2) *Data Ingestion Frameworks*: The data ingestion module acts as a central conduit — or multi-tenant hub — that enables the seamless transfer of data from different source systems to specific destinations and ensures reliable delivery without data loss. These sources can include third-party applications, databases or event-driven systems. Typically, this module is responsible for connecting external data inputs to big data platforms or data lakes (e.g. based on Hadoop) and supporting both batch and real-time streaming workflows for operations such as filtering, transformation and mapping.

3) *Data Analysis and Processing Frameworks*: The data processing and analysis phase plays a crucial role in preparing the data for downstream use by performing a number of operations, including transformation, enrichment, filtering, deduplication, mapping, cleansing, state management, joins, grouping, windowing, aggregation, staging and integrity validation. This phase also enables the integration of streaming and batch data to support unified analytics. The processing frameworks, which are located between the data ingestion and storage layers, serve as the engine for extracting values and structures from the raw data before it is persisted.

4) *Data Storage Frameworks*: Data storage forms a fundamental layer within the data pipeline and serves as a repository for processed and raw data. Storage solutions are generally categorized into three main types: relational database systems, data lakes and data warehouses.

5) *Data Monitoring and Visualization Frameworks*: Data monitoring and visualization are essential components to gain actionable insights. Effective visualization techniques allow users to recognize patterns, identify correlations and interpret trends or seasonal fluctuations — especially in telecom data sets. These tools not only support exploratory analysis, but are also crucial in the creation of routine performance reports. They help to clearly communicate both analytical results and raw data in an intuitive and meaningful format.

6) *Data orchestration and management frameworks*: The growing adoption of microservices and cloud-native orchestration tools is driven by their benefits, such as optimised service discovery and effortless horizontal scalability. Despite this momentum, the data engineering and infrastructure

landscape remains highly fragmented with little sign of converging into a unified framework. As the ecosystem continues to grow with the introduction of new distributed databases, platforms and development libraries, data management frameworks play a critical role in unifying these components through well-designed APIs. The overall goal is to simplify operations by enabling the provisioning and coordination of compute resources, services or containers through minimal API interactions, ultimately reducing complexity and operational overhead.

III. ROLE OF BLOCKCHAIN FOR B5G TECHNICAL ASPECTS

Blockchain's decentralized architecture enables participants in all industry sectors and 5G/6G-enabled IoT environments to contribute and access data directly from peer nodes without relying on centralized control or intermediaries. This peer-to-peer model increases transparency and enables all stakeholders in the 5G ecosystem to independently validate transactions, ensuring traceability, accountability and tamper-proof records through capabilities such as provenance and non-repudiation. Given these capabilities, it is becoming increasingly important to explore the potential of blockchain in softwareized network infrastructures and the associated use cases, benefits and challenges.

A. Application of Blockchain for B5G Use cases

1) *Dynamic Spectrum Management (DSM)*: Blockchain plays a transformative role in DSM by addressing critical limitations of traditional centralized models [3]. It introduces decentralization, enabling secure and fair spectrum access without relying on third-party administrators. The inherent transparency and immutability of blockchain ensure tamper-proof records and foster trust among stakeholders. Smart contracts automate processes such as allocation and trading, reducing manual intervention and risks of manipulation. Spectrum resources can be tokenized for transparent and efficient marketplace operations. Blockchain also supports the verification of spectrum ownership using NFTs, which simplifies authentication and reduces conflicts [4].

2) *AI/IoT data Management*: Blockchain plays a pivotal role in enhancing AI/IoT data management within emerging 5G and 6G networks by enabling a secure, decentralized, and intelligent framework for

data exchange, validation, and trust. Traditional IoT systems struggle with issues such as data manipulation, lack of real-time trust verification, and centralized vulnerabilities. Blockchain addresses these challenges by integrating machine learning techniques—such as support vector machines and ensemble validators—for real-time assessment of data trustworthiness, while smart contracts automate reputation scoring and secure transactions.

3) *Federated Network Slicing*: Blockchain offers a transformative solution to the challenges of infrastructure sharing in 5G and 6G networks, particularly within federated slicing scenarios. As mobile network operators (MNOs) lease their infrastructure to various service providers and infrastructure providers, dynamic and trustworthy resource allocation becomes essential. Blockchain enables decentralized and automated agreements using smart contracts, removing reliance on centralized authorities and reducing costs imposed by intermediaries [5].

B. Challenges of Blockchain Integration

Despite its potential, blockchain faces challenges such as scalability, high energy consumption, vulnerability to specific attacks, and lack of standardized frameworks. Addressing these issues through optimized consensus algorithms, off-chain solutions, and collaboration with standardization bodies is crucial for harnessing blockchain's full capabilities in spectrum management. Ultimately, blockchain provides a promising paradigm to enhance spectrum efficiency, transparency, and trust in the evolving 6G ecosystem.

IV. EXAMPLE DEMONSTRATIONS

A. Blockchain for Spectrum Violation Detection

Dynamic Spectrum Access (DSA) offers a flexible solution to the problem of underutilized radio frequencies in wireless networks. However, DSA introduces challenges in monitoring unauthorized access and ensuring trustworthy spectrum usage, especially when stakeholders are untrusted. Blockchain technology can provide transparency, integrity, and automation without relying on a central authority. To this end, the Distributed-Proof-of-Sense (DPoS) consensus algorithm [6] was designed specifically for spectrum sharing environments. It incentivizes nodes to sense and collect real-time spectrum data as part of block generation, enabling

reliable spectrum monitoring and misuse detection. The demonstration [7] showcases how spectrum-sensing nodes—using HackRF SDRs and Raspberry Pi devices—participate in a blockchain network built with Substrate. Through elliptic curve-based zero-knowledge proofs, nodes validate blocks containing sensed data, which are hashed on-chain and stored off-chain[6], [8]. This practical implementation illustrates how blockchain can support secure, decentralized, and automated detection of spectrum violations in future 5G/6G environments.

B. Blockchain-Based Trustworthy IoT Data Management

In IoT systems, ensuring data reliability is crucial, particularly for AI-based decision-making in critical applications like smart cities or healthcare. While blockchain can ensure data immutability and traceability, it cannot inherently verify the accuracy of the data being recorded. To address this, ML techniques are integrated with blockchain to evaluate the trustworthiness of IoT data before it is stored [9], [10]. A composite trust model combines historical sensor reputation with real-time ML-based classification to dynamically assess data quality. The demonstration [11], [12] presents a system where IoT sensors send data to edge servers for classification via Support Vector Machines (SVM), and validators further verify uncertain records using ensemble ML models like Random Forest and MLP. Trust-labeled data is stored on IPFS, while only the hashes are written to the blockchain. This approach, implemented using Hyperledger Fabric, illustrates how blockchain and AI can collaboratively ensure data integrity, trust, and scalability in decentralized IoT networks aligned with 5G/6G visions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this tutorial, we offered an in-depth exploration of the evolving intersection between data engineering and blockchain technologies, with a particular focus on their implications for B5G telecommunication systems. By examining each stage of the data engineering pipeline—ranging from data ingestion and processing to orchestration and visualization—and linking them with blockchain’s decentralized capabilities, we provided a holistic understanding of how these ecosystems can co-evolve to meet future telecom demands. Additionally, by

connecting these frameworks to broader data science paradigms and supporting our discussion with practical use cases and two demonstrative examples, this tutorial aimed to equip researchers and practitioners with the foundational insights needed to innovate within the rapidly transforming landscape of telecommunications.

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